

Development The Culture Of Book Reading

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Abstract: *The article is devoted to highlighting the specific features of the proper selection of literary works, independent reading and organization of extracurricular activities in order to interest students in reading. Also, the culture of reading books is manifested in the ability of students to transfer the knowledge obtained from artistic works to life, to use them in educational and any other practical activities, in public work, and in interpersonal relations. In this regard, the effective aspects of organizing independent work are highlighted.*

Keywords — Reader, art of reading, reading culture, reading core, text comprehension, extracurricular activities, independent reading, independent activities.

INTRODUCTION

The culture of reading books is considered as a manifestation and criterion of not only the literary and aesthetic maturity of a person, but also social and civil maturity, and the process of forming the culture of reading (reading) and then the culture of receiving information is an undoubted condition for its social, moral and aesthetic development. - condition, is seen as a condition directly related to the acquisition of creative reading skills and competencies. S. Kambarova said, "The need to form a culture of reading is not only related to the fact that students learn something new from literature. The process of independent reading is the realization of the national identity, the essence of life, It reflects socio-ethical and aesthetic ideals, improving towards common goals such as strengthening the civic duty and moral point of view. The art of reading is a creative, personal spiritual activity of the student. This activity determines the educational value of reading in advance, affects the general spiritual, ideological and moral development of the student, and the creative potential of the student's personality.

The main body

The concept of reading culture includes the interrelated questions of what to read, how to read, how to use what is read, and how much to read. Today, the concept of "book reading core" should be included among the methodological terms. This core contains a list of authors and works that are definitely required reading.

The reader should be able to acquire certain knowledge and skills related to obtaining information from the book, such as synopsis, quotations, excerpts, use dictionaries and reference books. "Understanding what is read and being able to describe one's attitude in oral and written forms - entries in a personal diary, reviews, articles for a wall newspaper, creative essays-miniatures, discussion-essays, short reviews, conversations about books, annotations and so on". "It is in this process that accustoming students to independent analysis of the read passage plays an important role". It is also helpful to give them several topics to research the passage on.

R.A. Dekusheva divides teenage readers into several groups according to the level of literary and aesthetic development. " The first group - readers with a receptive level of reading culture: the literary text being read or listened to is perceived in verbal and spiritual inactivity... Most of these readers often perceive and understand the text by distorting the meaning. The majority of students in this group cannot say anything about what they read or hear. The second group - readers with a reproductive, constructive level of reading culture: they can partially re-express (repeat) what they have read or memorized. Some of the students of this group show an attempt to introduce the elements of productive reading activity while re-expressing the read or listened text. The third group is the readers whose culture of reading and perception is at a productive level: the reader creates his own version of the retelling, willingly expresses his opinions about what he has read. This creative level of reading culture is rare in national schools: one or two students in one class, and not even in all classes" [Dekusheva: p. 10].

Reading a book is closely related to acquiring reading culture. When a reader chooses a book, he first looks at its title. He ponders over the issue posed in the title. It suggests what kind of problem it might be. Then he looks at the beginning of the word, flips through the book itself.

In works of art, there is almost no preface reflecting historical-literary information. This situation is not considered a violation of the alphabetic rules of the methodology. If we stand in the position of a book, the consistency of reading is in its natural path. He first reads the book, and then, if he liked the book, now he is interested in the author and everything else related to what he read. Any knowledge is actively received only when a question arises in the mind, and then the search for an answer begins.

Students need to be able to understand an important source as soon as they read it. Reading books outside of class (workout) helps with this, provides a factor to follow the periodical press, creates a thorough ground. If the habit of working with books, documents and periodical press materials is not formed at school, the process of independent reading of works of art will be difficult for the expert at the next stages, he will remain in a vortex of difficulties and tensions.

Observations show that not all teachers give enough importance to reading books outside of class. Some of them hand out wonderful literary works during class as an extra assignment to students who master well or are gifted. In this case, they use a small story separated from the collection, a fragment taken from the work on a separate paper, material published in a newspaper or magazine. Sometimes students are given the task of reading them at home. We would suggest here that it is appropriate to select as many excerpts as possible from one larger work of art, as well as excerpts from various sources. Firstly, the readers will have a more holistic impression of this work, and secondly, the actions of the characters, positive and negative sides, artistic aspects of the whole work will be revealed during the conversation. Experiences fully confirm this.

However, the observations show that the teacher is not literally directing this kind of study. The types of work envisaged in extracurricular studies are almost never realized. Collections of works intended for extracurricular reading have not been published, and their approximate lists have not been compiled. Special research is required in this regard. First of all, such materials should be available to the teacher.

It is better to start reading books outside of class with small works, fragments. After all, "Short stories are convenient for working: one can be read aloud, read the most interesting parts of the other, and offer to read to the end at home. For the third, it is necessary to ask questions in advance that will encourage them to read. It is possible to refer to the selective reading of several stories united by their common theme and problems: let the children read different stories, then the discussion of the topic will be more interesting".

Curiosity breeds curiosity. Psychologists divide interest into two main types: "interest to know and interest to participate". Interest in knowledge is expressed in receiving and processing information. Because of the desire to participate, one becomes immersed in the life experiences of others. When reading a work of art, both types of interest are intertwined. But, the author says, if there is no interest, there will be no reading. That's why a wonderful introductory conversation about the book (excerpt from the work) to be read is necessary. At this point, it is necessary to correctly assess the effect of interest in reading books on activity. 2-3 weeks are allotted for extracurricular reading, depending on the size of the excerpt from the work. In the meantime, the teacher gives relevant advice to the students. At this time, it is necessary to pay serious attention to maintaining the interest of students during reading. Some unfamiliar words in the passage should be explained in Uzbek language classes.

V.K.Veselova talks about extracurricular activities and distinguishes several of their principles: "1) interrelationship of classroom and extracurricular activities on Russian and native literature; 2) to gradually complicate the content of the lessons and, accordingly, the content of the independent work done by the students before the lesson; 3) consistency and interrelationship of work methods, methods and types representing different forms of students' and teachers' activity

; 4) unification of individual and collective work of students on the text of a literary work".

According to recommendations in methodological literature, the following types of work are conducted in grades V-VII: writing a short description of the main characters of the read work; to speak a brief summary of the read work; extracting from the text. Recommended activities in grades VIII-IX, academic lyceums and vocational colleges: evaluation of the work; write an annotation; creative writing.

Reading experience is determined not only by the number of works read, but also by the quality of their mastery. It is also necessary to use simple forms of creating reading experience and observations of students: expressive reading, providing information about the author, a short retelling of the plot, analyzing the scene, telling a story about a favorite character, commenting on illustrations.

In addition, "...students of the class receive individual and group tasks depending on their knowledge and interests: 1) preparation of news (information); 2) preparing a book exhibition; 3) cards; 4) reference work; 5) vocabulary work. Strong (talented students are assigned tasks in the description of conducting research: 1) comparison; 2) description".

In regional and district educational institutions where reading is widely popular, there are great opportunities to hold reading conferences, debates, contests, and quizzes.

There are different opinions in the teaching methodology of Russian literature about the volume of works recommended for students to read outside of class. According to the recommendation of L.A. Sheiman, 5–20 pages in grades II–IV (5–10 in grade II, 10–15 in grade III, 15–20 in grade IV); 20–70 pages in grades V–VII (20–30 in grade V, 30–45 in grade VI, 45–70 in grade VII); 70–150 in VIII-X classes (70–90 in VIII class, 90–120 in IX class, 120–150 in X class). The author admits that these are not normative indicators, but only hints. In general, you should read at least one hour at home.

Continuity is ensured by reading every day. There is also another side of the issue: in the beginning of the larger passages, more attention is paid to word learning, in the later ones, due to the nature of repeated use, the previous lexicon changes rapidly, and unfamiliar words decrease. As a result, texts gradually increase in size. Of course, there are many academic subjects studied by students of academic lyceums and vocational colleges. In our opinion, studying for an hour 2-3 days a week is enough. At first, reading the work and using the dictionary to understand its content is done. According to L.A. Sheiman, a detailed dictionary of the work should be recommended. Then work on questions and assignments.

Before the lesson, which is held outside the classroom, the teacher conducts conversations with the students. Paying attention to how they understood the passage, he plans the work to be done in the lesson and makes corrections to the plan he made. It also explains some words they don't know. It helps to understand the meaning of some sentences. It is also appropriate for the teacher to tell about these events when the

excerpt taken from the work requires clarification of the same events that were reflected in the previous parts.

The teacher seriously prepares for extracurricular studies: he prepares an introduction, makes a lesson plan, and leads it. Such a lesson has the goal of summarizing the work done on what has been read. "Also, with the intention of increasing the independence of students, the class is held in the form of reading commentary or in the form of a lesson-conversation and exchange of ideas. In addition to his ability to express his own opinions, the independence of the reader is manifested in his "ability to accept the opinions of those who argue with him"

The stage of reading a book read at home begins with a conversation about the author of the work. Then there will be a question and answer about the content of the passage. Students' information (output) is listened to. The teacher concludes this part of the lesson with his final words.

Conversations about what has been read should not be limited to retelling the plot. It is important to master the ideological content of the work while understanding the cause-and-effect relationships. Therefore, it is necessary to establish problem-based education. The teacher should teach the students to think, observe, and prove with the help of questions encouraging them to discuss what they have read. For this, the teacher should ask more "What do you think? Why...?" should ask questions like Even if the minute of reading a book outside of class is not big, it is better to focus on the discussion of one work.

The ideological-thematic analysis of a literary work is carried out in depth, as during the study of ordinary literary material, but on a general plan, without a detailed textual study of each part. The teacher should not stop the students at every step, and should not correct every unclear statement. First of all, it is necessary to feel freedom in the lesson.

Recommendation classes organized on the basis of the book fair are of great importance in order to organize the next extracurricular study. In this case, taking some classes in the library is not without benefits: the student gets to know more about the available books. One work inspires to read another.

"When determining the type of training, it is necessary to proceed from the content of the educational material, the educational and didactic goals of learning it, and the methods of activity of the teacher and students determined by these goals; also, one should not be indifferent to the place of a specific training in the general system of other trainings". "Extracurricular reading hours can be successful as a result of extensive preparatory work by the teacher and independent work of students based on their own choices and interests. First, the teacher determines the ideological and communicative problem of the lesson. And this (due to the limitation of time) requires a selective approach to knowledge and content, abandoning the analysis of the work at all stages". The size of the material and the goals of its study determine the methodical and structural organization of the training.

"If students can imagine the structure of the lesson, the description of the work carried out in the classroom, the sense

of responsibility for their participation in it, conditions are created for comparing the results achieved by one student with the results of his peers, the moral relationships necessary for a person entering life (mutual support, mutual control, common concern for work) experience is formed. This moral aspect of extracurricular reading hours is very important. In addition, this organization of work allows to get rid of overload: each student prepares only for one issue or part, but at the same time has an idea about the topic and course of the lesson in general and can participate in the discussion of other issues".

When talking about extracurricular reading classes, it is impossible not to touch on their type and appearance. As it is explained in the book "Uroki vneklassnogo chteniya", "...the type of lesson reflects its main educational, didactic and educational-aesthetic direction, and the appearance shows the specific organizational forms of the implementation of this direction" 6 . Conducting independent creative research on the work represents such a direction.

According to M. Mirqosimova, "During independent creative research, students communicate with each other and ask the teacher questions about their research. The teacher is aware of the direction of their independent creative research, gives the necessary advice, and directs the students' activities. As the deadline approaches, the students' independent creative researches are also coming to an end. The teacher gets acquainted with their independent opinions, fills the necessary places, organizes the final training". Advises to organize lectures of students on the writer's life and work, abstract works on some works.

The teacher should take into account what the students should pay attention to while conducting independent creative research and give the necessary advice. According to M. Mirkosimova, these tips will consist of the following:

1. Paying attention to the historical conditions and the literary environment of that time when getting acquainted with the information about the life of the creator.
2. To determine what actual social and spiritual issues of the time are reflected in the work created by the writer and the creator's attitude towards them.
3. Comparative study of various works in assessing the writer's artistic skills based on the requirements of artistry and authenticity.
4. To pay attention to the importance of literary traditions, creative influence and personal research that influenced the formation of the artist's style.
5. Use of literature that illuminates the writer's life and work (according to the teacher's recommendation)² .

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Conclusion

It is clear from the above points that the minutes of reading a book outside of class can educate and form students' need, passion, and interest in reading, as well as the ability to think about what they have read, to understand the main problems raised by the author, and to search for answers to many vitally important questions from the book.

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